

Apache Sunrise Ceremony

also known as “Apache Sunrise Dance”, “Na-ih-es / Na'ii'ees”

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Native American (North American) Religions, Language, Athabaskan-Eyak-Tlingit, Athabaskan-Eyak, Athabaskan

The Apache Sunrise Ceremony is not exclusively practiced by one Apache tribe, although its more well-established iterations are those of the Mescalero Apache and the White Mountain Apache of the Western Apache. The Sunrise Ceremony is an intensive four-day coming-of-age ritual in which an Apache girl is culturally initiated into womanhood. This is a highly important and spiritually charged rite that reflects Apache origins and cosmivision.

Date Range: 1800 CE - 2026 CE

Region: Historic Apache Territories

Region tags: North America, United States of America, U.S. Southwest, Northern New Mexico

General geographic range of the key historic Apache regions: Mescalero, Chiricahua, Lipan, Jicarilla, Plains and Western Apache. The geographic area indicated is not completely that of the Apache and many non-Apache tribes live throughout, particularly the Puebloan people.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Site

Does the ritual take place in an outside setting?

ID:
8880

– Yes

→ Enclosed?

ID:
8881

– No

↳ Elevated? ID: 8882
– No

↳ By a body of water? ID: 8883
– No

↳ Near fire (e.g., volcano, lava, human-made fire)? ID: 8884
– Yes
Notes: Evening dances are centered around a controlled fire.

↳ In a location considered holy? ID:
8885
– Yes

↳ Other [Specify] ID: 8886
– N/A

Does the ritual take place in an inside setting? ID:
8887
– Yes

↳ Underground? ID: 8888
– No

↳ Is there an acknowledgment or reference to the elements or materials from
which the setting is created? (e.g., wood or stone for a building) ID: 8889
– Yes

Is the ritual carried out in a public place? ID:
8890
– No

Is the ritual carried out in a private place? ID: 8892

– Yes

Is there a specific site or building associated with this ritual?

ID: 8893

– No

Is the site associated with this ritual considered sacred?

ID: 8894

– Yes

Was the site associated with this ritual created?

ID:
8895

– Yes

↳ Was it temporary?

ID: 8896

– Yes

↳ Was it permanent?

ID:
8897

– No

Was the site associated with this ritual found?

ID: 8898

– Yes

↳ Through divination:

ID: 8899

– Yes

↳ Through astronomical observation:

ID: 8900

– No

↳ Through myths, legends or literature:

ID: 8901

– Yes

Is the site associated with a metaphysical concept?

ID: 8902

– Yes

Is the site representative of another physical or metaphysical space?

ID:
8903

– Yes

Is the site oriented to the sun, stars, or other astronomical features?

ID:
8904

– Yes

Does the site have a particular directional orientation (e.g., N, S, E, W)?

ID: 8905

– Yes

Is the site oriented to landforms (e.g., mountains, rivers, coast, etc.)?

ID:
8906

– Yes

Frequency

How often is this ritual performed?

ID: 8907

– Yes

↳ Annually:

ID:
8908

– No

↳ Daily:

ID:
8909

– No

↳ Weekly:

ID: 8910

– No

↳ Seasonally:

ID: 8911

– No

↳ Once in an individual's lifetime: ID: 8912
– Yes

Notes: This occurs once in a person's life during the cultural designated moment of entering womanhood.

↳ Special events/occasions: ID: 8913
– No

↳ During life cycle events (marriage, birth, death, etc.): ID: 8914
– Yes

↳ Ad hoc: ID: 8915
– No

Is the duration of the ritual unspecified? ID: 8916
– No

Is the duration of the ritual specified? (If so, include the range of duration in hours) ID: 8917
– Yes: 96

Participants

Are there agent(s) involved in this ritual? ID: 8918
def: this includes the enactor(s) of the ritual and/or entity or entities responsible for the efficacy of the ritual
– Yes

↳ How many agents are involved in this ritual? ID: 8919
– Yes: 3

Notes: At least three principle participants - the young female initiate entering womanhood as well as at least two shamans (one female and one male), not including the participation of family members, and Apache Crown / Ga'an Dancers

- ↳ Are agents of specific gender/sex for this ritual? ID: 8920
– Yes
- ↳ Are they male: ID: 8921
– Yes
Notes: Typically one male shaman to officiate the ritual
- ↳ Are they female: ID: 8922
– Yes
Notes: The young female initiate and the female shaman to physically guide the female initiate
- ↳ Are they transgender: ID: 8923
– No
- ↳ Are they non-binary: ID: 8924
– No
- ↳ Are they other: ID: 8925
– No
- ↳ What is the age range of agents in this ritual? ID: 8926
– N/A
Notes: Shamans within the various Apache nations can vary in age, though more often than not wisdom and experienced is associated with seniority
- ↳ Do agents have to have biological distinctiveness for this ritual? ID: 8927
(e.g., twin, born breach, albino, mental illness, hermaphrodite, blind, other disability)
– No
- ↳ Do agents have to have a specific social role for this ritual? ID: 8928

(e.g., widow, unmarried, etc.)

– Yes

↳ Are agents required to be insiders for this ritual? ID: 8929

– Yes

↳ Are agents initiated? ID: 8930

– Yes

Notes: Shamans are already initiated into their role as medicine specialists. The female tribe member who is the focus of the respective Sunrise Ceremony is in the process of being conferred womanhood and adulthood through this ritual

↳ Are agents part of the social group? ID: 8931

– Yes

↳ Other: ID: 8932

– N/A

↳ Are agents required to be outsiders for this ritual? ID: 8933

– No

↳ Are agents required to be specialists for this ritual? ID: 8934

– Yes

Notes: The shamans are revered medicine specialists of their respective communities

↳ Are agents non-specialists for this ritual? ID: 8935

– Yes

Notes: The female initiate herself is not a specialist

↳ Are there specific prohibitions for agents in this ritual? ID: 8936

(e.g., menstruating women, men of a certain age)

– Physical state (e.g. menstruation, illness): No sleep, no personal care, no emotion, no sustenance

Notes: The respective female initiate must fast, not touch water, suppress emotion, not tend to personal grooming (the female shaman attendant assists with the basics of this), and must not sleep for the duration of the ritual

- ↳ Are there supernatural agents associated with this ritual? ID: 8937
– Yes
- ↳ Are they deceased humans: ID: 8938
– No
- ↳ Are they non-human, organic entities: ID: 8940
– No
- ↳ Are they abiotic or inorganic entities: ID: 8944
– No
- ↳ Are they divine/spiritual beings: ID: 8948
– Yes
- ↳ Are they high gods: ID: 8949
– Yes
- ↳ Are they mixed divine (high-god)/human beings: ID: 8950
– No
- ↳ Are they transformed/self-cultivated humans: ID: 8951
Definition: humans who have undergone deliberate efforts to change/refine/develop/transform themselves.
– Yes

↳ Other:

ID: 8952

– N/A

Are there patient(s) involved in this ritual?

ID:

Definition: recipient, beneficiary, client, target, victim of ritual

8953

– No

Are there participants other than the agent involved in this ritual?

ID: 8989

Definition: besides the agent, other actively participating in ritual, by responding, singing, dancing, interacting with ritual agents

– Yes

↳ How many participants are involved in this ritual?

ID:

– N/A

8990

Notes: This varies by community and family size. Attendees are invited, and there are a host of individuals that contribute to stages of this event.

↳ The participants' gender/sex is:

ID:

– No

8991

↳ What is the age range of participants in this ritual?

ID:

– N/A

8997

↳ Do participants have a specific social role for this ritual?

ID: 8998

– Yes

Notes: It depends. There are family and community supporters, but there are also specialist Apache Crown Dancers to facilitate spiritual dances to help keep the female initiate awake

↳ Are participants required to be insiders for this ritual?

ID: 8999

– Yes

Notes: It is an exceptional rarity for non-Apache to be invited to these ceremonies. It can occur, but

it is not common

- ↳ Are participants required to be outsiders for this ritual? ID: 9000
– No
- ↳ Are participants required to be specialists for this ritual? ID: 9001
– No
- ↳ Are participants non-specialists for this ritual? ID: 9002
– Yes
- ↳ Are there specific prohibitions for participants to take part in this ritual? ID: 9003
– No
Notes: The female initiate is more of an agent than simply a participant. Thus the attendees are better phrased as participants, and they do not have the same prohibitions as the initiate.
- ↳ Are there supernatural beings that act as participants in this ritual? ID: 9004
– Yes
 - ↳ Are they deceased humans: ID: 9005
– No
 - ↳ Are they non-human, organic entities: ID: 9007
– No
 - ↳ Are they abiotic or inorganic entities: ID: 9011
– No
 - ↳ Are they divine/spiritual beings ID: 9015
– Yes

↳ Are they high gods: ID: 9016

– Yes

Notes: White Painted Woman - the primary deity responsible for creation within the Apache spiritual worldview. There are also Ga'an (Sacred Mountain Spirits) that are channeled through Apache Crown Dancers.

↳ Are they mixed divine (high-god)/human beings: ID: 9017

– No

↳ Are they transformed/self-cultivated humans: ID: 9018

– No

↳ Others: ID: 9019

– No

Are there spectators in this ritual? ID: 9020

Definition: not actively participating in ritual or required to perform any actions

– Yes

↳ How many spectators observe this ritual? ID: 9021

– Field Doesn't Know

Notes: Spectators are one-and-the-same as participants. Spectators fuel the spiritual energy necessary for the female initiate to complete her Sunrise Ceremony.

↳ The spectators' gender/sex is: ID: 9022

– No

↳ What is the age range of spectators in this ritual? ID: 9028

– N/A

Notes: It is the range of ages of the community.

- ↳ Do spectators have a specific social role for this ritual? ID: 9029
– No
- ↳ Are spectators required to be insiders for this ritual? ID: 9030
– Yes
Notes: Typically yes, but there are occasional exceptions for respected outsider guests.
- ↳ Are spectators required to be outsiders for this ritual? ID: 9031
– No
- ↳ Are spectators required to be specialists for this ritual? ID: 9032
– No
- ↳ Are spectators non-specialists for this ritual? ID: 9033
– Yes
- ↳ Are there specific prohibitions for spectators to take part in this ritual? ID: 9034
– No
- ↳ Are there supernatural beings that act as spectators in this ritual? ID: 9035
– No

Cause/Trigger

- Is this ritual practiced at will? ID: 9051
– No
- Is participation obligatory? ID: 9054
– Yes
- ↳ Consequences of non-participation: ID:

– Field Doesn't Know

9055

Notes: There may be some social stigma between peer community members for not attending to support the female initiate, but the female initiate must participate and transform into womanhood or otherwise she would not be culturally considered an adult

Is this ritual practiced as part of an event?

ID: 9061

– Yes

Notes: The event itself is the Sunrise Ceremony - which lasts for four days, however the overall preparation necessary for this along with the ceremony itself is a total of 12 days on average

Is this ritual practiced as part of calendric or astrological causes/events?

ID: 9062

– No

Is this ritual triggered by hemerological considerations (system of favorable/unfavorable days)?

ID:
9063

– No

Is the ritual practiced in response to seasonal change?

ID:
9064

– No

Is the ritual practiced in response to specific natural events (e.g., drought, ecological death, etc.)?

ID: 9065

– No

Is the ritual practiced in response to specific social events (e.g., death of a leader, etc.)?

ID:
9066

– No

Is the ritual performed in reaction to an ominous event?

ID: 9067

– No

Is this ritual practiced during a specific life stage?

ID:
9070

– Yes

- ↳ Does this ritual take place to aid conception? ID: 9071
 - No
- ↳ Does this ritual take place immediately postpartum? ID: 9072
 - No
- ↳ Does this ritual take place during a marriage? ID: 9073
 - No
- ↳ Does this ritual take place during pregnancy? ID: 9074
 - No
- ↳ Does this ritual take place during the coming of age period? ID: 9075
 - Yes
 - Notes: This is specifically a coming of age ceremony for Apache women
- ↳ Does this ritual take place at the time of entrance to the religious group? ID: 9076
 - No
- ↳ Does this ritual take place in preparation for death? ID: 9077
 - No
- ↳ Does this ritual take place after death? ID: 9078
 - No
- ↳ Is this ritual practiced during other social status changes? ID: 9079
 - No

↳ Other: ID: 9080
– N/A

Is this ritual part of another ritual? ID: 9081
– No

Is this ritual financially sponsored by non-participants? ID:
9083
– No

Purpose

Is the purpose of this ritual for maintenance? ID:
9089
– No

Is the purpose of the ritual to cause a change? ID: 9090
– Yes

↳ Is the change expected to be positive: ID: 9091
– Yes

↳ Is the change expected to be negative: ID: 9092
– No

↳ Is the change expected to be neutral: ID: 9093
– No

↳ Select the type of change: ID:
9094
– Social
– Cultural
– Spiritual

What is the domain involved in this ritual?

ID: 9095

– Yes

↳ Is it divine/spiritual:

– Yes

ID:

9096

↳ Is it non-human organic entities (e.g., nature, animals, plants):

– Yes

ID: 9097

↳ Is it abiotic/inorganic entities (and objects):

– No

ID:

9098

↳ Is it ecological:

– Yes

ID: 9099

↳ Is it transformed humans:

– Yes

ID:

9100

↳ Is it for knowledge transmission (e.g., oral storytelling):

– Yes

ID: 9101

↳ Other:

– N/A

ID: 9102

Is there a specific goal(s) associated with this ritual?

ID: 9103

– Yes

↳ Is devotion a goal of the ritual?

– No

ID: 9104

- ↳ Is creation of a cultural product a goal of this ritual? ID: 9121
– No
- ↳ Is propitiation a goal of this ritual? ID: 9122
– No
- ↳ Is domestication of agents a goal? ID:
9123
Definition: temporary or permanent transformation of an inimical or indifferent target into something beneficial for practitioners.
– No
- ↳ Is this ritual practiced to gain information? ID:
9124
– No
- ↳ Is this ritual practiced for cosmic maintenance? ID:
9128
– No
- ↳ Is this ritual practiced for ecological maintenance and/or stewardship? ID: 9129
– No
- ↳ Is this ritual practiced for self-transformation? ID: 9135
– Yes
- ↳ To become god-like: ID:
9136
– No
- ↳ To become immortal: ID: 9137
– No
- ↳ To achieve divine or superhuman attributes: ID:

- No 9138
- ↳ For salvation/liberation from the world: ID: 9139
 - No
- ↳ For spiritual cleansing: ID: 9140
 - Yes
- ↳ To achieve moral perfection: ID: 9141
 - No
- ↳ For an initiation into a new status: ID: 9142
 - Yes
- ↳ To achieve a change in mental state: ID: 9143
 - No
- ↳ Is this ritual practiced as a way to express gratitude to a god or other supernatural agents? ID: 9147
 - Yes
- ↳ Is this ritual performed for purification? ID: 9148
 - Yes
- ↳ Is it physical: ID: 9149
 - Yes
- ↳ Is it mental: ID: 9150
 - Yes
- ↳

- ↳ Is it emotional: ID: 9151
– Yes
- ↳ Other: ID: 9152
– N/A
- ↳ Is this ritual practiced for exorcism purposes? ID: 9153
– No
- ↳ Is this ritual practiced for health/healing purposes? ID: 9158
– No
- ↳ Is this ritual practiced to transmit information? ID: 9181
– Yes
- ↳ Is this ritual practiced to obtain luck (generic)? ID:
9182
– No
- ↳ Is this a naming ritual? ID:
9183
– No
- ↳ Is this ritual practiced to improve the community's modes of subsistence? ID: 9184
– No
- ↳ Is this ritual practiced to induce harm? ID:
9193
– No
- ↳ Is this ritual practiced for protection purposes? ID: 9209
– No

- ↳ Is this ritual associated with warfare or ritual contests (e.g., stick ball games)? ID: 9218
– No
- ↳ Is this ritual associated with craft practices (e.g., weaving, etc.)? ID: 9219
– No
- ↳ Is this ritual associated with infanticide? ID: 9220
– No
- ↳ Is this ritual associated with gambling/games of chance? ID: 9221
– No
- ↳ Is this ritual associated with travel? ID: 9222
– No
- ↳ Is this ritual associated with social relations? ID: 9223
– No
- ↳ Is this ritual practiced to obtain wealth or success? ID: 9231
– No

Is the causal efficacy assessed? ID: 9239
– No

Techniques

Is sound practiced during this ritual? ID: 9243
– Yes

Is it considered "music" in the local culture/community? ID: 9244

– Yes

Is this sound coordinated with movement?

ID:
9245

– Yes

↳ Is it oral?

ID: 9246

– Yes

↳ Is it communal? (e.g., choir)

ID:
9247

– Yes

↳ Is it individual?

ID: 9248

– No

↳ Is there a call and response?

ID: 9249

– Yes

↳ It involves singing:

ID: 9250

– Yes

↳ It involves chanting:

ID: 9251

– Yes

↳ it involves invocation/prayer:

ID: 9252

– Yes

↳ It involves mantras:

ID: 9253

– Yes

↳ It involves wailing/cheering (heightened emotional expression):

ID:

– Yes 9254

↳ It involves narrative/recitation: ID: 9255

– Yes

↳ It involves whistling: ID: 9256

– Yes

↳ It involves shouting/loud vocalizations: ID: 9257

– No

↳ Is the sound produced with parts of the body? ID: 9286

– No

↳ Are there instruments/objects involved in creating sounds for the ritual? ID: 9315

– Field Doesn't Know

Is movement involved in this ritual? ID:

– Yes 9345

↳ Is it considered "dance" by the culture that practices this ritual? ID: 9346

– Yes

↳ Is it coordinated with sound? ID: 9347

– Yes

↳ Does it involve the use of objects? ID: 9348

– Yes

↳ How many individuals are involved in this movement ID: 9349

– N/A

Is there regalia/ornamentation used as part of this ritual?

ID: 9382

– Yes

↳ Are there specific body markings done for the ritual?

ID: 9383

– No

↳ Is there hair regulation as part of this ritual?

ID: 9386

– No

↳ Is there tooth modification involved in this ritual?

ID: 9389

– No

↳ Are individuals partly or fully naked as part of this ritual?

ID: 9390

– No

↳ Are scars made as part of this ritual?

ID:
9391

– No

↳ Are piercings made as part of this ritual?

ID: 9393

– No

↳ Does genital modification take place during this ritual?

ID:
9395

– No

↳ Do individuals have to wear specific clothing for this ritual?

ID: 9402

– Yes

↳ Are there specific shoes to be worn for this ritual?

ID:

– Yes 9403

↳ Is there a head covering used during the ritual? ID: 9404

– No

↳ Are the clothing colors regulated for the ritual? ID: 9407

– Yes

↳ Are there specific clothing items restricted for exclusive use in the ritual? ID: 9408

– Yes

↳ Are there jewelry/charms used during this ritual? ID: 9409

– Yes

↳ Are masks used during the ritual? ID: 9410

– Yes

Notes: The Apache Crown Dancers are masked

Are there materials/objects used in this ritual? ID: 9411

– Field Doesn't Know

Does consumption take place as part of this ritual? ID: 9475

– No

Does the ritual stimulate an altered state of consciousness? ID: 9545

– Yes

↳ Does the individual retain biographical identity? ID: 9546

– Yes

↳ Does the individual retain control of the body? ID: 9547
– Yes

↳ Does it involve spirit travel? ID: 9556
– Yes

↳ Where does the spirit travel to? ID: 9557
– N/A

↳ Is the individual chosen (e.g., by a supernatural agent)? ID: 9558
– Yes

↳ Is there a method of induction? ID: 9559
– Field Doesn't Know

Notes: The method of induction is the completion of the four-day ceremony, pushing the initiate's to their mental, physical, and emotional limits without sleep or rest

Are offerings involved as part of this ritual? ID: 9567
– Field Doesn't Know

Notes: The event itself is exceptionally costly in terms of financial and social debt. The event itself is the offering for White Painted Woman to help the young female initiate transform into Apache womanhood.

Are non-normative practices involved in this ritual? ID:
– Field Doesn't Know 9621

Formal Features

Does the ritual stand by itself? ID: 9689
– Yes

Is the ritual part of a sequence of rituals? ID:
9690

– No

Is the repetition of the ritual determinate (e.g., an action must be repeated a certain number of times)?

ID:
9691

– No

Is the repetition of the ritual non-determinate?

ID: 9692

– Yes

Compared to everyday non-ritual behavior, what is the level of repetition?

ID: 9693

– High

Compared to everyday non-ritual behavior, what is the level of rigidity of this ritual?

ID: 9694

– High

Compared to everyday non-ritual activity, what is the level of arousal of this ritual?

ID:
9695

– High

Compared to everyday non-ritual activity, what is the level of physical activity in this ritual?

ID: 9696

– High

Is there behavioral conformity?

ID:
9697

– Yes

↳ What is the level of behavioral conformity

ID: 9698

– High

Is there synchrony in this ritual?

ID: 9699

– Yes

↳ Are the roles differentiated? ID: 9700
– Yes

Is there entrainment in this ritual? ID: 9701
– No

Is there coordination in this ritual? ID: 9707
– Yes

↳ What is the level of coordination? ID: 9708
– High

↳ Is there movement/sound/attention? ID: 9709
– Yes

Is there preparation time needed to carry out this ritual? ID: 9710
– Yes
Notes: Up to 8 days

How many hours are involved in the ritual preparation? ID: 9711
– Specify: 192

Are there preparation activities involved? ID: 9712
– Yes

↳ Does it involve fasting: ID: 9713
– Yes

↳ Does it involve purification: ID: 9714
– Yes

↳ Does it involve learning/training: ID: 9715
– Yes

↳ Does it involve penance: ID: 9716
– No

↳ Does it involve abstention: ID: 9717
– Yes [specify]: Abstaining from sleep, sustenance, personal care

Is practice/expertise required to carry out this ritual? ID: 9718
– Yes

What is the level of expertise required? ID: 9719
– High

What is the level of economic cost involved to practice this ritual? ID: 9720
– Yes

↳ In local currency: ID: 9721
– N/A

↳ Number of people or days of labor equivalent: ID: 9722
– Specify: 12

↳ Other measure of cost: ID: 9723
– Specify: Community participation

What is the transmission mode of the ritual? ID:
– Vertical 9724
– Horizontal

How is the ritual transmitted?

ID: 9725

– In oral form

Who or what has authority over this ritual?

ID:

– Divine beings

9726

– Religious specialists

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